

Fighting antibiotic resistance: We can do better!

Antibiotic resistance is a global threat to health and development. But the way we behave can either slow this process down or speed it up. Antibiotic resistance is a collective problem. It is also a shared responsibility. And it is not limited to medical antibiotic use. Whether it is choices made in the dairy aisle or by ensuring vaccinations are up-to-date before travelling, the effectiveness of our efforts to curb antibiotic resistance will depend on our behaviour. We need to raise awareness of how individuals' actions contribute to antibiotic resistance and learn why they use antibiotics responsibly, why they sometimes do not, and what encourages them to do better.

>> Our collective responsibility

Making sure we have antibiotics that work is a matter of justice. The Swedish public thinks it is unfair to deplete a resource and leave people in need without it. Antibiotic resistance is not just seen as a public health issue but also a matter of moral relevance.

The collective responsibility of maintaining antibiotic effectiveness is mirrored in the individual's responsibility to make decisions and act in a way that promotes the maintained effectiveness of antibiotics and behave sensibly and responsibly, engaging in what Mirko Ancillotti and his colleagues call judicious antibiotic behaviour.

If people are informed about antibiotic resistance and learn about how resistance can be slowed down, they can include this kind of considerations in their own decision-making and be willing to act for maintaining antibiotic effectiveness. Despite

the personal disadvantage, people are prepared to change their behaviour if it means that their actions can help antibiotic resistance slow down.

Whether someone behaves judiciously or not depends not only on how the individual wants to behave: the influence of socio-economic, contextual and collective determinants needs to be acknowledged, because using antibiotics responsibly, and taking decisions that prevent antibiotic resistance, cannot be reduced to a matter of individual awareness and goodwill alone. Institutions need to create conditions that can facilitate individuals to make decisions that allow them to act responsibly.

How? >>

>> Creating the right conditions

There are many ways our behaviour can contribute to slowing down the development of antibiotic resistance. Informing people about the problems that misuse of antibiotics can cause, or the benefits of vaccination is helpful. Curbing antibiotic resistance requires a global approach, with coordinated actions. For the general public, this means understanding that our behaviour comes with consequences for our loved ones and ourselves, but also affects people globally. At the policy level, it means making sure the public is informed and can act in favour of maintaining antibiotic effectiveness.

>> Recommendations

Develop health communication based on an assessment of people's attitudes, beliefs, and the social norms that influence whether people use antibiotics responsibly and whether they take preventative action against antibiotic resistance in other areas of their lives. Our research showed that while virtually everyone is concerned about antibiotic resistance, their motivations to minimize their contributions to antibiotic resistance are diverse.

Some responded better to altruistic messages about avoiding to contribute to the worsening of antibiotic resistance, while others showed to be more influenced by considerations of economic nature. Sending different messages to different publics, and utilising welfare benefits to motivate people to act for, rather than against, maintained antibiotic effectiveness can be an effective tool.

Include messages about the effects of individual health behaviour alongside messages about the public health and moral dimensions of antibiotic resistance in public campaigns. And show that people's individual health decisions can contribute to slowing down antibiotic resistance. For example, our research showed that older adults are particularly aware of and attentive to the secondary effects of antibiotic treatment. Other people showed high solidarity and altruistic attitudes and were particularly concerned about the unfairness of abusing antibiotics and leaving few therapeutic options to future patients.

Involve the public in the design and implementation of effective programmes to maintain the effectiveness of antibiotics.

The desire of being part of the solution as a community was clearly stated by many participants in our research.

Emphasise the fact that antibiotic-resistant bacteria are already a significant public health issue. This is equally important in the design of campaigns to inform the public and in doctor-patient communication. Our research clearly shows that while antibiotic resistance is considered a serious health threat, it is not clear to the public how this threat can actually affect their lives. Instead, people view it as a future concern or a problem that only affects other countries.

Highlight how individuals' can contribute to mitigating or worsening the general situation, but also how it comes with consequences for the individual themselves, their loved ones, their colleagues, and their neighbours. Our research shows that there are different ways of nudging people towards sensible and responsible antibiotic behaviour. Although actions to maintain antibiotic effectiveness depend on the collective taking action, individual behaviour should be highlighted. To capitalise on this, communication should target different levels (e.g. the individual, family, community, national & global level). By framing antibiotic resistance as a global problem, people might feel far away from it and struggle to see how they can make a difference by making responsible choices in their everyday lives. But seeing how they can contribute to the slowing down of antibiotic resistance might motivate them to act responsibly and act to prevent it.

>> About these policy recommendations

These recommendations are meant to support those looking to develop communication strategies to raise awareness of antibiotic resistance and encourage responsible use of antibiotics. These recommendations are directed to:

- Individuals and organisations working in health information, health education, and risk communication, such as Folkhälsomyndigheten (the Public Health Agency of Sweden) and Livsmedelsverket (the Swedish Food Agency).
- Individuals and organisations working to prevent the rise of antibiotic resistance, such as ReAct or STRAMA – the Swedish strategic programme against antibiotic resistance.
- Health care professionals who meet patients in their daily life (physicians, nurses, pharmacists), SFAM – the Swedish association of general practice, the Swedish Medical Association, Apotekarsociteten – the Swedish Pharmaceutical Society, Läkartidningen.
- Researchers in the field of global health, public health, education, and communication.

>> Further reading

Ancillotti, M. (2021) [Antibiotic resistance: a multimethod investigation of individual responsibility and behaviour](https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1520759&dswid=7281). Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis, Uppsala, Sweden. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1520759&dswid=7281>

Ancillotti, M., Eriksson, S., Veldwijk, J., Nihlén Fahlquist, J., Andersson, D. I., and Godskesen, T. (2018). [Public awareness and individual responsibility needed for judicious use of antibiotics: a qualitative study of public perception and behavior](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-6047-8). BMC Public Health, 18:1153. DOI: 10.1186/s12889-018-6047-8

Ancillotti, M., Eriksson, S., Godskesen, T., Andersson, D. I., and Nihlén Fahlquist, J. (2020). [An effort worth making: A qualitative study of how Swedes respond to antibiotic resistance](https://doi.org/10.1093/phe/phaa033). Public Health Ethics, phaa033. DOI: 10.1093/phe/phaa033

Ancillotti, M., Eriksson, S., Andersson, D. I., Godskesen, T., Nihlén Fahlquist, J., Veldwijk, J. (2020). [Preferences regarding antibiotic treatment and the role of antibiotic resistance: A discrete choice experiment](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijantimicag.2020.106198). International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents, 56(6):106198. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijantimicag.2020.106198

Ancillotti, M., Nihlén Fahlquist, J., Eriksson, S. (2021). [Individual moral responsibility for antibiotic resistance](https://doi.org/10.1111/bioe.12958). Bioethics, DOI: 10.1111/bioe.12958

>> About the researcher

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